

NUPs and the Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS)

Netherlands University Presses (NUPs):

- Consortium of progressive, open-access academic publishers
- Based in the Netherlands
- Support diamond open access
- Aim to deliver high-quality scholarly and educational content that is freely accessible to everyone.
- Six presses: Leiden University Press, Maastricht University Press, Open Press TiU, Radboud University Press, TU Delft OPEN Publishing, University of Groningen Press

Diamond Open Access Standard (DOAS) from European Diamond Capacity Hub:

- Technical guide, tool and benchmarking resource
- Offers comprehensive guidelines for institutional publishers and service providers (IPSPs)
- Offers a self-assessment tool to evaluate publishing standards
- Promotes equitable, transparent and high-quality diamond open access
- Addresses seven core components: 1. funding, 2. Legal ownership, mission and governance, 3. Open Science, 4. editorial management, editorial quality and research integrity, 5. technical service efficiency, 6. visibility, communication, marketing and impact, 7. equity, Diversity, Inclusion and Belonging (EDIB), multilingualism and gender equity

What we did: Five of the NUPs completed the [DOAS self-assessment tool](#) from April to December 2025. We compiled the results and highlighted the areas where the NUPs are performing strongly and where they need to focus.

Strong performance (highlights)

Financials:

- No paywalls and transparency about financials
- Funded by public funds
- Independent editorial operations

Governance:

- Owned by not-for-profit academic or scholarly organizations
- Defined ownership statements of journals published
- Transparency about ownership and offer information about their ownership structure on their website

Open science:

- Transparency on rights retention publication policy
- Allow the dissemination of article preprints
- Journals are published with an open license
- Implement a rights retention policy
- Comply with Open Access mandates
- Open Access journals

Technical:

- Persistent identifiers for published items & registration
- Publicly display archival and digital preservation policy
- Well-maintained publishing platforms with basic functionalities that comply with the security standards
- Publishing platforms that support online submission, editorial, and publishing workflows

Areas for improvement

Editorial Management and Quality

- Items needing attention are publishing timelines, manual of style, guidelines for reviewers and authors, lack of endogeneity, communication procedures between journal and the publisher

Visibility and Impact

- NUPs need to work on discoverability of content and indexing

Equity, Diversity, Inclusion, and Belonging (EDIB)

- Content is not multilingual
- Journals don't publish in more than one language
- Journals don't yet require equity in submissions and decisions